

NORMAL CHANGES: ASSOCIATED WITH AGEING IN HUMAN BEING

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Abstract

Ageing is commonly characterized by a progressive, generalized impairment of physiochemical and biological aspects of cellular body functions for an increasing vulnerability to environmental challenges and a growing risk of disease and death. Wrinkled skin and sagging facial muscles due to less collagen and elastin produced by fibroblast are usually observed with ageing. People may become fatigued more easily because of increased cardiac work to maintain oxygen levels in the body, accumulation of cholesterol on the walls of the arteries and decreased ability to replace fluids lost while breathing: above changes, may need more rest. In dehydration case, adequate fluid intake should be assured and medical help should be sought. Learning new information may take longer for an older person and they may need clues to help retrieve information stored in memory.

Keywords:

Ageing, Longevity genes, Pharmacodynamic changes, Pharmacokinetic changes.

INTRODUCTION

Ageing is commonly characterized by a progressive, generalized impairment of physiochemical and biological aspects of cellular body functions for an increasing vulnerability to environmental challenges and a growing risk of disease, long-term morbidity and potentially mortality. Wrinkled skin and sagging facial muscles due to less collagen and elastin produced by fibroblast are usually observed with ageing. As cells mature, they naturally stop dividing and enter into a period called cellular senescence. In response to DNA damage (shortened telomeres) cells either senescence or self destruct (apoptosis), if the damage cannot be repaired. In elder persons, debilitating skeletal muscle defect characterized by a loss of viable mass, and onset of a decrease in muscle strength and force generation can often lead to complete immobilization. The concentration of oxidative damaged proteins, lipids and DNA molecules increase in diseases with the human ageing. Ageing induces defect in mitochondrial electron transport chain in nigrostriatal pathway and manifestations similar to Parkinson's disease by impairing energy metabolism in dopaminergic neurons. In elder persons, debilitating skeletal muscle defect characterized by a loss of viable mass, and onset of a decrease in muscle strength and force generation can often lead to complete immobilization. Many body organs in elder persons are reduced in size and are abnormally brown caused by excessive amounts of lipofuscin, a granular brown wear and tear intracellular pigment associated with excessive usage of an organ.

Ageing results in physiological (pharmacokinetic) changes that affect the absorption, metabolism, distribution and elimination of drugs. Age related changes in gastrointestinal tract, liver and kidneys include reduced gastric acid secretion, gastrointestinal motility, total surface area of absorption, splanchnic blood flow, liver size, liver blood flow, glomerular filtration and liver tubular filtration. In frail debilitated elderly patients, activities of plasma-esterases and hepatic glucuronyltransferases may be impaired. Even minor reductions in first pass metabolism can result in significant increase in bioavailability (rate and extent of drug availability in systemic circulation) consequently clinical effect of drug such as hypotensive effect of nifedipine. The age-related physiological changes which may affect drug distribution are reduced lean body mass, total body water, increased total body fat, lower serum albumin level and α_1 -acid glycoprotein level unchanged or slightly raised. Increased body

fat results in an increased volume of distribution for fat soluble compounds (clomethiazol, diazepam and thiopental) whereas reduction in body water results in a decrease in distribution volume of water-soluble drugs (cimetidine, digoxin and ethanol). Plasma albumin levels decrease with age, free fraction of acidic drugs (cimetidine, furosemide and warfarin) will increase. Anticholinergic drugs may cause urinary retention in elder men especially associated with prostatic hypertrophy. Anti-cholinergic drugs, opiates, tricyclic antidepressants, antihistamines are more likely to cause constipation or ileus. Aspirin, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug used to reduce reoccurrence of non-fatal strokes is more likely to cause gastroduodenal ulceration and bleeding in the elderly.

Molecular and cellular (pharmacodynamic) changes that occur with ageing may alter the response to the drugs due to a reduction in homeostatic reserve and change in specific receptor and target sites. α_2 -adrenoceptor responsiveness appears to be reduced with ageing. In normal elderly subjects there is blunting of reflex tachycardia. Anticholinergics, hypnotics, H_2 -antagonists and β -blockers cause confusion. Geriatrics (elderly people over 65 years of age) is more sensitive to benzodiazepines, warfarin and adverse effects of digoxin. Reduction in dosage of drugs (warfarin, digoxin and aminoglycosides) with a low therapeutic index (risk-benefit ratio) but not in dosage of drugs (penicillin) with a high therapeutic index is necessary. Constipation, senile and multi-infarct dementia, confusion, urinary incontinence as stress, overflow and detrusor instability in elderly person and urethral dysfunction more prevalent in elderly women are the common problems. Furosemide, loop diuretic may cause incontinence in such patients.

Clearance of hepatically eliminated drugs is impaired due to morphological change rather than impaired enzymatic activity. Understanding age-related changes in pharmacodynamic factors, avoiding poly-pharmacy and regular and critical review of all drug treatment will help in the rationalizing of drug prescribing, reduction in drug-related morbidity and also the cost of drug therapy for elderly patients especially those aged over 75 years.

These time-related changes are attributed to the aging process. This process may be common to all living things, for the phenomenon of aging and death is universal. If so, both aging and the rate of the aging process are under genetic control to some extent for the manifestations of aging, and life span differs between species and individual members of a species. Further, like all chemicals and chemical reactions, the manifestations of aging which reflect chemical composition and the rate of the aging process should be subject to environmental influences.

The nature of the aging process has been the subject of considerable speculation. The major theories of aging (e.g. the free radical theory, the immunologic theory (1), the inflammation theory (2), mitochondrial (3) theories are all specific of a particular ageing. The sum of the deleterious free radical reactions going on continuously throughout the cells and tissues constitutes the aging process or is a major contributor to it. In mammalian systems the free radical reactions are largely those involving oxygen.

FREE REDICAL THEORY OF AGING

Fig.1 The free radical theory.

The free radical theory (4-8) of aging assumes that there is a single basic cause of aging, modified by genetic and environmental factors, and postulates that free radical reactions are involved in aging and age-related disorders. These reactions arise upon exposure to ionizing radiation, from non-enzymatic reactions, and from enzymatic reactions, particularly those of the two major energy-gaining processes employed by living things-photosynthesis (9) and the reduction of O₂ to water (10-12). They probably also arise as well in the reduction of some terminal electron acceptors employed by anaerobes, probably with NO₃ (13, 14), possibly with CO₂ (13), and maybe with SO₄²⁻ (13). Although this theory is applicable to all life, the following comments are directed largely to mammalian aging, in which O₂ is the main source of damaging free radical reactions, because of the importance attached to slowing the aging process in man. Dietary manipulations expected to further lower the rate of production of free radical reaction damage, briefly summarized recently, give results in accord with the free radical theory of aging. For example, dietary antioxidants increase the life span of mice (14), rats (15), fruit flies (16), nematodes and rotifers, as well as the "lifespan" of neurospora (Fig.1).

MITOCHONDRIAL THEORY OF AGING

Fig.2 Mitochondrial theory of aging.

The age-related physiological decline seems to be due to the accumulation of defects in the several metabolic pathways. Looking for potential candidates to progressive accumulation of damage over a lifetime, it seems reasonable to exclude RNA, proteins and other cellular macromolecules with a rapid turned over. For this main reason, studies exploring mechanisms of aging have always been focused on DNA. In mammalian cells, mitochondria and the nucleus are the only organelles possessing DNA. It appears obvious that the physiological integrity of the cell is strongly linked to the integrity of its genome. Even if mitochondrial DNA comprises only 1%–3% of genetic material in animal cells, its contribution to cellular physiology seems to be much greater than what expected from its size alone. Mitochondrial DNA, in close proximity to the sites of oxygen radical production and unprotected by the histones that are associated with nuclear DNA, is a sensitive target for oxygen radical attack (Fig. 2).

In fact, it has been estimated that the level of oxydatively oxidized bases in mitochondrial DNA is 10- to 20-fold higher than that in nuclear DNA (17); Moreover, mitochondrial DNA encodes polypeptides of the electron transfer chain as well as components required for their synthesis. Therefore, any coding mutations in mitochondrial DNA will affect the entire electron transfer chain, potentially altering both the assembly and function of the products of numerous nuclear genes in electron transfer chain complexes.

GENE REGULATION THEORY OF AGING

Fig. 3. Genotypic frequency by age in genes not associated with lifespan (A), longevity genes (B), and aging genes (C) (Modified form Barzilai et al., 2010).

The gene regulation theory of aging proposes that senescence is the resulting of changes occurring in the gene expression (17). Although it is clear that many genes show changes in expression with age, it is unlikely that selection could act on genes that promote senescence directly (18). unknown how the proteins coded by these genes are acting in the regulation of longevity. On the other hand, other studies At least 15 different genetic manipulations inducing life extension in organisms such as yeast, fruit flies, nematodes, and mice have been demonstrated (19). However, it is still performed using animal models have suggested that genes supposed to be involved in aging are not able to reverse or arrest the inexorable expression of the molecular disorder (22) depicted in Fig. 3 that is the hallmark of aging (20).

AGING AND GENES

The lifespan of individual organisms varies based on species. The maximum lifespan for humans is currently 120 years, atmost. The maximum lifespan in each species is determined by genes (Table 1).

Table 1 Genes associated with longevity.

Genes	Longevity	Biological action
Klotho (KL gene)	+	Insulin sensitivity, modulation of vitamin D
Silent mating type information regulation 2 homolog 1 (SIRT1)	+	Regulates epigenetic gene silencing and suppresses recombination of rDNA
Adiponectin (AdipoQ)	+	Modulates glucose and fatty acid metabolism
APOC-3	-	Inhibits lipoprotein lipase and hepatic lipase
Cholesterylesters triglyceride protein (CETP)	-	Facilitates the transport of cholesteryl esters triglycerides between the lipoproteins
Thyrotropinreceptor (TSHR)	-	Production of T4 and T3
Thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH β)	+	Production of TSH
Growth hormone (GH)	+	Stimulates growth, production of IGF-I
IGF-I/insulin (FOXO)	+	Transcription factors that take part in cell growth and differentiation
Mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR)	-	Modulates insulin, IGF, and mitogen function
Catalase (CAT)		Antioxidant that protects cells from hydrogen peroxide

Do longevity genes that increase maximum life-span exist? If such longevity genes exist, what is the function of these genes in the human body? Perpetual youth and longevity is a dream of people worldwide, and extensive research is currently being performed to clarify the mechanism of aging using new molecular and genetic methodologies to identify for longevity genes (21) (fig.4)

Fig. 4 Implementation of the National Institute for Longevity Sciences, Longitudinal Study of Aging (NILS-LSA).

Aging cells

As cells age, they function less well. Old cells sometimes die because they are programmed to do so. The genes of cells program a process that, when triggered, results in death of the cell. This programmed death, called apoptosis, is a kind of cell suicide. The aging of a cell is one trigger. Old cells must die to make room for new cells. Other triggers include an excess number of cells and possibly damage to a cell. This limit is programmed by genes. When a cell can no longer divide, it grows larger, exists for a while then dies. (28).

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Aging organs

How well organs function depends on how well the cells within them function. Older cells function less well. Also, in some organs, cells die and are not replaced, so the number of cells decreases. The number of cells in the testes, ovaries, liver, and kidneys decreases markedly as the body ages. When the number of cells becomes too low, an organ cannot function normally. Thus, most organs function less well as people age. However, not all organs lose a large number of cells. The brain is one example. Healthy older people do not lose many brain cells. Substantial losses occur mainly in people who have had a stroke or who have a disorder that causes the progressive loss of nerve cells (neurodegenerative disorders), such as Alzheimer disease or Parkinson disease. The first signs of aging involve the musculoskeletal system. The eyes, followed by the ears, begin to change early in mid-life. Most internal functions also decline with aging. Most bodily functions peak shortly before age 30 and then begin a gradual but continuous decline. However, even with this decline, most functions remain adequate because most organs start with considerably more functional capacity than the body needs (functional reserve). For example, if half the liver is destroyed, the remaining tissue is more than enough to maintain normal function. Thus, disorders, rather than normal aging, usually account for most of the loss of function in old age.(30).

Muscles and Body Fat

The amount of muscle tissue (muscle mass) and muscle strength tend to decrease beginning around age 30 and continuing throughout life. Some of the decrease is caused by decreasing levels of growth hormone and testosterone, which stimulate muscle development. Also, muscles cannot contract as quickly because more fast-contracting (fast-twitch) muscle fibers are lost than slow-contracting (slow-twitch) muscle fibers. However, aging's effects reduce

muscle mass and strength by no more than about 10 to 15% during an adult's lifetime. More severe muscle loss (called sarcopenia, which literally means loss of flesh) results from disease or extreme inactivity, not from aging alone. By age 75, the percentage of body fat typically doubles compared with what it was during young adulthood. Too much body fat can increase the risk of health problems, such as diabetes. The distribution of fat also changes, changing the shape of the torso. A healthy diet and regular exercise can help older people minimize increases in body fat (28).

Bones and Joints

Ageing related bone diseases are categorized in three major classes, the *erosion of the joint or osteoarthritis*, a low bone mass disease, *metastatic bone diseases* that relate to breast cancer in women or prostate cancer in men and *organ atrophy*. Bones tend to become less dense. Thus, bones become weaker and more likely to break. In women, loss of bone density speeds up after menopause because less estrogen is produced. Estrogen helps prevent too much bone from being broken down during the body's normal process of forming, breaking down, and re-forming bone. Bones become less dense partly because they contain less calcium (which gives bones strength). The amount of calcium decreases because the body absorbs less calcium from foods. Also, levels of vitamin D, which helps the body use calcium, decrease slightly. Certain bones are weakened more than others. Those most affected include the end of the thighbone (femur) at the hip, the ends of the arm bones (radius and ulna) at the wrist, and the bones of the spine (vertebrae).

Changes in vertebrae at the top of the spine cause the head to tip forward, compressing the throat. As a result, swallowing is more difficult, and choking is more likely. The vertebrae become less dense and the cushions of tissue (disks) between them lose fluid and become thinner, making the spine shorter. Thus, older people become shorter. The cartilage that lines the joints tends to thin, partly because of the wear and tear of years of movement. The surfaces of a joint may not slide over each other as well as they used to, and the joint may be slightly more susceptible to injury. Damage to the cartilage due to lifelong use of joints or repeated injury often leads to osteoarthritis, which is one of the most common disorders of later life. Ligaments, which bind joints together, and tendons, which bind muscle to bone, tend to become less elastic, making joints feel tight or stiff. These tissues also weaken. Thus, most people become less flexible. Ligaments tend to tear more easily, and when they tear, they heal more slowly. These changes occur because the cells that maintain ligaments and tendons become less active.

Hair

Hair loss and graying are commonly associated with aging. Receding hairlines and thinning of the hair are common by age 50, especially for men. Graying tends to vary by ethnic groups and individuals.

Eyes

As people age, The lens stiffens, making focusing on close objects harder and lens becomes denser, making seeing in dim light harder. The pupil reacts more slowly to changes in light. The lens yellows, changing the way colours are perceived and number of nerve cells decrease, impairing depth perception. The eyes produce less fluid, making them feel dry. Loss of near vision during their 40s, most people notice that seeing objects closer than 2 feet becomes difficult. This change in vision, called presbyopia, occurs because the lens in the eye stiffens. Normally, the lens changes its shape to help the eye focus. A stiffer lens makes focusing on close objects harder. Ultimately, almost everyone gets presbyopia and needs magnifying reading glasses. People who need glasses to see distant objects may need to wear bifocals or glasses with variable-focus lenses. Less light passes through to the retina at the back of the eye. Also, the retina, which contains the cells that sense light, becomes less sensitive. So for reading, brighter light is needed. On average, 60-year-olds need 3 times more light to read than 20-year-olds.

Ears

Most changes in hearing are probably due as much to noise exposure as to aging. Exposure to loud noise over time damages the ear's ability to hear. Nonetheless, some changes in hearing occur as people age, As people age, hearing high-pitched sounds becomes more difficult. This change is considered age-associated hearing loss (presbycusis). For example, violin music may sound less bright. Older people may think that other people are mumbling. Even when other people speak more loudly, older people still have difficulty understanding the words. The reason is that

most consonants (such as k, t, s, p, and ch) are high-pitched, and consonants are the sounds that help people identify words. Because vowels are lower-pitched sounds, difficult than understanding what men say because most women and children have higher-pitched voices. Gradually, hearing lower pitches also becomes more difficult.

Mouth and Nose

Generally, when people are in their 50s, the ability to taste and smell starts to gradually diminish. Both senses are needed to enjoy the full range of flavors in food. The tongue can identify only five basic tastes: sweet, sour, bitter, salt, and a relatively newly identified taste called umami (commonly described as meaty or savory) and as well as people age, taste buds on the tongue decrease in sensitivity. This change affects tasting sweet and salt more than bitter and sour. The ability to smell diminishes because the lining of the nose becomes thinner and drier and the nerve endings in the nose deteriorate. However, the change is slight, usually affecting only subtle smells. Because of these changes, many foods tend to taste bitter, and foods with subtle smells may taste bland. The mouth tends to feel dry more often, partly because less saliva is produced. Dry mouth further reduces the ability to taste food. The gums recede slightly. Consequently, the lower parts of the teeth are exposed to food particles and bacteria. Also, tooth enamel tends to wear away. These changes, as well as a dry mouth, make the teeth more susceptible to decay and cavities (caries) and thus make tooth loss more likely. With aging, the nose tends to lengthen and enlarge, and the tip tends to droop. Thick hairs may grow in the nose and on the upper lip and chin.

Teeth

While we may lose a few teeth, with proper dental care, teeth should last a lifetime. As we age, our teeth become more sensitive to hot and cold temperatures. Tooth decay, gum disease and discoloration of teeth occur with age.

Skin

The skin tends to become thinner, less elastic, drier, and finely wrinkled. However, exposure to sunlight over the years greatly contributes to wrinkling and to making the skin rough and blotchy. People who have avoided exposure to sunlight often look much younger than their age and skin changes partly because the aging body produces less collagen (a tough, fibrous tissue that makes skin strong) and elastin (which makes skin flexible). As a result, the skin tears more easily. The fat layer under the skin thins. This layer acts as a cushion for the skin, helping protect and support it. The fat layer also helps conserve body heat. When the layer thins, wrinkles are more likely to develop, and tolerance for cold decreases. The number of nerve endings in the skin decreases. As a result, people become less sensitive to pain, temperature, and pressure, and injuries may be more likely. The number of sweat glands and blood vessels decreases, and blood flow in the deep layers of the skin decreases. As a result, the body is less able to move heat from inside the body through blood vessels to the surface of the body. Less heat leaves the body, and the body cannot cool itself as well. Thus, the risk of heat-related disorders, such as heatstroke, is increased. Also, when blood flow is decreased, the skin tends to heal more slowly.(28)

Brain and Nervous System

Elder person don't lose overall ability to learn new things but there are changes in the learning process. Aged person is harder to memorize lists of names and words than for a younger person. Sensory and motor changes as well as cognitive ability may affect ability to respond – hard to know which is which. Discourage long naps and caffeinated products later in the day – encourage the same patterns and rituals at bedtime support changes in nervous system.

Ageing causes changes to the brain size, vasculature, and cognition. Sleep /wake cycle changes at 60/70 may need 1 or 2 less hours of sleep at night but sleep may not be as restful. People get about 20% less oxygen to the brain which affects balance. The brain shrinks with increasing age and there are changes at all levels from molecules to morphology. Incidence of stroke, white matter lesions, and dementia also rise with age, as does level of memory impairment and there are changes in levels of neurotransmitters and hormones. Protective factors that reduce cardiovascular risk, namely regular exercise, a healthy diet, and low to moderate alcohol intake, seem to aid the ageing brain as does increased cognitive effort in the form of education or occupational attainment. A healthy life both physically and mentally may be the best defence against the changes of an ageing brain. Additional measures to prevent cardiovascular disease may also be important.

The number of nerve cells in the brain typically decreases. However, the brain can partly compensate for this loss in several ways such as cells are lost, new connections are made between the remaining nerve cells and new nerve cells may form in some areas of the brain, even during old age and the brain has more cells than it needs to do most activities—a characteristic called redundancy. Levels of the chemical substances involved in sending messages in the brain change. Most decrease, but some increase. Nerve cells may lose some of their receptors for messages. Blood flow to the brain decreases. Because of these age-related changes, the brain may function slightly less well. Some mental functions—such as vocabulary, short-term memory, the ability to learn new material, and the ability to recall words—may be subtly reduced after age 70. After about age 60, the number of cells in the spinal cord begins to decrease. Usually, this change does not affect strength or sensation.

Heart and Blood Vessels

The heart and blood vessels become stiffer. The heart fills with blood more slowly. The stiffer arteries are less able to expand when more blood is pumped through them. Thus, blood pressure tends to increase and differences between young and old hearts become apparent only when the heart has to work hard and pump more blood—for example, during exercise or an illness. An older heart cannot speed up as quickly or pump as fast or as much blood as a younger heart. Thus, older athletes are not able to perform as well as younger athletes. However, regular aerobic exercise can improve athletic performance in older people. Blood pressure should be monitored (32).

Muscles of Breathing and the Lungs

The muscles used in breathing, such as the diaphragm, tend to weaken. The number of air sacs (alveoli) and capillaries in the lungs decreases. Thus, slightly less oxygen is absorbed from air that is breathed in. The lungs become less elastic. In people who do not smoke or have a lung disorder, these changes do not affect ordinary daily activities, but these changes may make exercising more difficult. Breathing at high altitudes (where there is less oxygen) may also be harder. The lungs become less able to fight infection, partly because the cells that sweep debris containing microorganisms out of the airways are less able to do so. Cough, which also helps clear the lungs, tends to be weaker.(29)

Digestive System

The digestive system is less affected by aging than most other parts of the body. The muscles of the oesophagus contract less forcefully, but movement of food through the oesophagus is not affected. Food is emptied from the stomach slightly more slowly, and the stomach cannot hold as much food because it is less elastic. But in most people, these changes are too slight to be noticed. Certain changes cause problems in some people. The digestive tract may produce less lactase, an enzyme the body needs to digest milk. As a result, older people are more likely to develop intolerance of dairy products (lactose intolerance). People with lactose intolerance may feel bloated or have gas or diarrhoea after they consume milk products. In the large intestine, materials move through a little more slowly. In some people, this slowing contributes to constipation. The liver tends to become smaller because the number of cells decreases. Less blood flows through it, and liver enzymes that help the body process drugs and other substances work less efficiently (28).

Kidneys and Urinary Tract

The kidneys tend to become smaller because the number of cells decreases. Less blood flows through the kidneys, and at about age 30, they begin to filter blood less well. As years pass, they may remove waste products from the blood less well. They may excrete too much water and too little salt, making dehydration more likely. Certain changes in the urinary tract may make controlling urination more difficult such as the maximum volume of urine that the bladder can hold decreases. Thus, older people may need to urinate more often and the bladder muscles may contract unpredictably (become overactive), regardless of whether people need to urinate and the bladder muscles weaken. As a result, they cannot empty the bladder as well, and more urine is left in the bladder after urination and the muscle that controls the passage of urine out of the body (urinary sphincter) is less able to close tightly and prevent leakage. Thus, older people have more difficulty postponing urination.(28).

Reproductive Organs**Women**

The effects of aging on sex hormone levels are more obvious in women than in men. In women, most of these effects are related to menopause, when the levels of female hormones (particularly estrogen) decrease dramatically, menstrual periods end permanently, and pregnancy is no longer possible. The decrease in female hormone levels causes the ovaries and uterus to shrink. The tissues of the vagina become thinner, drier, and less elastic (a condition called atrophic vaginitis). In severe cases, these changes can lead to itching, bleeding, pain during intercourse and a need to urinate immediately (urinary urgency).

The breasts become less firm and more fibrous, and they tend to sag. This change makes finding lumps in the breasts more difficult. Some of the changes that begin at menopause (such as lower hormone levels and vaginal dryness) may interfere with sexual activity. However, for most women, aging does not greatly detract from enjoyment of sexual activity. Not having to worry about becoming pregnant may enhance sexual activity and enjoyment (31).

Men

In men, changes in sex hormone levels are less sudden. Levels of the male hormone testosterone decrease, resulting in fewer sperm and a decreased sex drive (libido), but the decrease is gradual. Although blood flow to the penis tends to decrease, most men can have erections and orgasms throughout life. However, erections may not last as long and may be slightly less rigid, or may require more stimulation to maintain. A second erection may require more time. Erectile dysfunction (impotence) becomes more common as men age and is often due to a disorder, usually a disorder that affects blood vessels (such as a vascular disease) or diabetes (31).

Endocrine System

The levels and activity of some hormones, produced by endocrine glands, decrease growth hormone levels, leading to decreased muscle mass and aldosterone levels decrease, making dehydration more likely. This hormone signals the body to retain salt and therefore water and Insulin, which helps control the sugar level in blood, is less effective, and less insulin may be produced. Insulin enables sugar to move from the blood into cells, where it can be converted to energy. The changes in insulin mean that the sugar level increases more after a large meal and takes longer to return to normal (31).

Blood Production

The amount of active bone marrow, where blood cells are produced, decreases. Therefore, fewer blood cells are produced. The bone marrow can usually produce enough blood cells throughout life. Problems may occur when the need for blood cells is greatly increased—for example, when anaemia or an infection develops or bleeding occurs. In such cases, bone marrow is less able to increase its production of blood cells in response to the body's needs (28).

Immune System

The cells of the immune system act more slowly. These cells identify and destroy foreign substances such as bacteria, other infecting microbes, and probably cancer cells. Cancer is more common among older people and vaccines tend to be less protective in older people. Some infections, such as pneumonia and influenza, are more common among older people and result in death more often and allergy symptoms may become less severe (29).

Aging changes in organs - tissue – cells

All vital organs begin to lose some function as you age during adulthood. Aging changes occur in all of the body's cells, tissues, and organs, and these changes affect the functioning of all body systems. Living tissue is made up of cells. There are many different types of cells, but all have the same basic structure. Tissues are layers of similar cells that perform a specific function and different kinds of tissues group together to form organs.

There are four basic types of tissue:

Connective tissue

Supports other tissues and binds them together. This includes bone, blood, and lymph tissues, as well as the tissues that give support and structure to the skin and internal organs.

Epithelial tissue

Epithelial tissue provides a covering for deeper body layers. The skin and the linings of the passages inside the body, such as the gastrointestinal system, are made of epithelial tissue.

Muscle tissue

Muscle tissue includes three types of tissue: striated muscles-such as those that move the skeleton (also called voluntary muscle), smooth muscles (also called involuntary muscle)-such as the muscles contained in the stomach and other internal organs and cardiac muscle which makes up most of the heart wall (also an involuntary muscle).

Nerve tissue

Made up of nerve cells (neurons) and is used to carry messages to and from various parts of the body. The brain, spinal cord, and peripheral nerves are made of nerve tissue (32).

Weight

Most of us gradually increase weight in our 30's and 40's. People in their 50's often notice a gradual decline in weight. Past age 50, there may be noticeable changes to one's face, legs and arms due to a reduction of fat (34).

CONCLUSION

Aging is a spiritual and psychological journey as well as a physical one. Everyone does not experience all of these changes. Weight loss or gain of 10 pounds in six months needs to be looked into medically. Foods rich in nutrition but lower in calories should be provided because older people need fewer calories. Sense of thirst decreases so help people to drink enough. Kidneys may also be filtering more medication. Handling physical stress becomes more difficult as one get older. People are less able to adjust to such stresses as heat, cold, physical exertion, and illness. Exercise helps to maintain bone density, to prevent muscle tissue from turning to fat prevent depression. Walking and other exercise should be Encourage as suggested by medical doctor or physiotherapist.

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